

Reviewer Acknowledgements

International Journal of Statistics and Probability wishes to acknowledge the following individuals for their assistance with peer review of manuscripts for this issue. Their help and contributions in maintaining the quality of the journal is greatly appreciated.

Many authors, regardless of whether *International Journal of Statistics and Probability* publishes their work, appreciate the helpful feedback provided by the reviewers.

Reviewers for Volume 6, Number 3

Ali Reza Fotouhi, University of the Fraser Valley, Canada
Chin-Shang Li, University of California, USA
Douglas Lorenz, University of Louisville, USA
Farida Kachapova, The Auckland University of Technology, New Zealand
Felix Almendra-Arao, UPIITA del Instituto Politécnico Nacional, México
Gane Samb Lo, University Gaston Berger, Senegal
Gerardo Febres, Universidad Simón Bolívar, Venezuela
Haiming Zhou, Northern Illinois University, USA
Hui Zhang, St. Jude Children's Research Hospital, USA
Jacek Białek, University of Lodz, Poland
Luiz Ricardo Nakamura, University of Sao Paulo, Brazil
Marcelo Bourguignon, Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Brazil
Maryam Eskandarzadeh, Persian Gulf Boshehr University, Iran
Nahid Sanjari Farsipour, Alzahra University, Iran
Philip Westgate, University of Kentucky, USA
Rebecca Bendayan, University College London, UK
Sajid Ali, Bocconi University, Italy
Shatrunjai Pratap Singh, John Hancock Financial Services, USA
Shuling Liu, Yale University, USA
Sohair F. Higazi, University of Tanta, Egypt
Subhradev Sen, Alliance University, India
Tomás R. Cotos-Yáñez, University of Vigo, Spain
Vyacheslav Abramov, Swinburne University of Technology, Australia
Zaixing Li, China University of Mining and Technology (Beijing), China

Wendy Smith

On behalf of,

The Editorial Board of *International Journal of Statistics and Probability*

Canadian Center of Science and Education